

MODELS AND NEW TRENDS IN THE PROCESS OF FORMING TOURIST FLOW IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines scientifically substantiated models of the process of forming tourist flows in the tourism market of Uzbekistan from the point of view of demand and develops a forecast of the types of tourism services the need for will increase and decrease by 2030 in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *tourism, tour operator, tour package, booking systems, travel agent, travel portal.*

Introduction. The tourism network is a huge socio-economic system operating within the national economy. Like any system, its individual elements, interactions between them are coordinated through the regulatory levers of the market economy. However, no matter how improved and perfect the tourist services market is, it cannot fully solve socio-economic problems such as training personnel for the tourism network, preservation and protection of historical and cultural heritage, environmental protection, ensuring the safety of tourists, and modernization of the transport system. These shortcomings in the market of tourist services can be eliminated by effective regulation by the state.

The regulation of the economy by the state means the activity of the state on the organization of the social production process aimed at achieving a general economic balance that ensures more effective use of limited production resources to increase the level of meeting the needs of members of society.

Revealing the content and essence of the market of tourist services and determining the place of regulation of its development by the state is of theoretical and practical importance and is aimed at increasing the efficiency of social production. In the history of economic thought, the question of the role of the state in the economy was considered on a scientific basis

As a result of the increasing penetration of digital technologies into tourism, fundamental changes have occurred in the processes of forming the tourist flow. As a result of empirical observations and research based on scientific sources, the author proposed 5 models of the process of forming tourist flows in the tourism market of Uzbekistan from the point of view of demand:

Initiative tour operator model. The tourist trip is organized in full cooperation with the proactive tour operator operating in the permanent place of residence of the potential tourist, and the receptive tour operator located in the tourist region where the tourist trip is organized, and is sold in the form of a tourist package, including hotel services, transport, guide, restaurant, etc. etc. If at a time when Internet technologies were not sufficiently developed and proactive tour operators did not have their own websites, clients turned to travel agencies to purchase a travel package, today this process is carried out without intermediaries. That is, the client has the opportunity to purchase a travel package using the digital sales channels of the initiative tour operator;

Model of a receptive tour operator. A tourist trip is remotely organized, in whole or in part, by a receptive tour operator working in the receiving party and involves the sale of at least three services (visa support, hotel, transport, etc.) at a single price in the form of a tourist package. This model became popular in the 21st century, when most potential tourists could purchase a travel package through sales channels (websites) created directly by the receptive tour operator (in

the tourist region in which the tourist trip is being organized), without having to contact the tour operator or travel agency, working in the tourist's permanent place of residence.

Model of reservation systems. In the second half of the 20th century, a limited group of people (tour operators, travel agencies, airline and railway ticket office employees) had access to Global reservation systems to purchase tickets for various means of transport and book hotels, as well as the formation of personal electronic systems tourism service providers; They are now gaining popularity in the form of websites and mobile applications with a compact interface that can be used by everyone, and this is expanding the scope of the tourism generation process. Modern tourists independently organize their trips to our country using global booking systems for air and railway tickets, road transport, hotels, restaurants and guide services (booking.com, trivago.com, needguide.ru) or local systems, that is, their own websites of tourism service organizations (eticket.uzrailway.uz, uzbooking.com).

Model of a tourist portal. This model provides for the formation of tourist flows through tourism portals created by marketing authorities at the national, regional and local levels, based on the concept of managing a tourist region as a destination. This model differs from others by the use of innovative methods based on the principles of the digital economy in managing the tourism industry at different levels, the use of internal resources to attract tourists, the localization of the bulk of income from the industry, and the participation of local players in the tourism market. This model makes it possible for countries with highly developed and developing tourism to use their tourism potential to create tourism portals at the national, regional or local levels and, through them, provide potential tourists with the opportunity to independently organize trips.

Local travel agent model. The category of tourists who prefer to stay in certain tourist places for a long time (guests visiting relatives, families in private mobile homes, people who decide to stay in a historical city for more than 3 days) choose the path of organizing their trip independently and, as a rule, are inclined to purchase mini-packages lasting from 3 to 10 hours through travel agents working in the visited tourist destination. This type of service is widely used in Egypt, Thailand, Singapore, Turkey, USA and other developed countries. Such companies are called "Destination Management Companies". As part of this business model, short-term travel packages are sold at the request of clients, which are usually not offered by macro-level tour operators.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process

Analysis and results. It should be noted that the above 5 models that form the tourist flow are active in practice, with the first and second models corresponding to the organized segment of the tourist flow in terms of supply, the third and fourth models satisfy the needs of the independently organized tourist segment. The fifth model is designed to meet the needs for mini-packages of both the self-organized tourist segment and the segment that purchases a tourist package through intermediaries. In addition, there is a tendency that the first two models are giving way to 3-4-5 models, which in turn indicates that Uzbekistan needs to take measures to adapt the tourism supply system to innovative segments, that is, create an infrastructure suitable for independent travelers organizing their trips through booking systems and travel portals.

The advent of digital media has had a significant impact on tourism. This situation can be characterized by the growing number of travelers planning their trips based on online travel agencies, digitally user-generated content, and other digital media. For example, in 2020, 59% of international travel undertaken by EU residents used digital means to book accommodation and 67% to purchase air tickets [1]. The number of UK tourists booking accommodation online has increased from 42% in 2010 to 52% in 2022. The sharp reduction in the number of physically

operating tour operators is proof of this. Thus, the number of travel agencies in the United States decreased from 25,975 organizations in 2000 to 14,797 in 2021, and employment decreased from 183,143 to 108,984 workers.

The following statistics show that digital platforms are increasingly used by tourists in the tourism industry. For example, booking.com operates in 190 countries and has 29 million accommodation properties located in 154,000 tourist destinations around the world.

Moreover, in a survey conducted by the State Committee for Tourism Development, only 12.8% of respondents (out of a total of 5,756) stated that they had traveled to Uzbekistan on a tour package. The majority of travelers using tour operator services are from European countries (38.6%) and Asia-Pacific (38.3%). The smallest number of tourists traveling along tourist routes in Uzbekistan, that is, 3.2% are citizens of the CIS and 3.7% of Central Asia.

As a result of Uzbekistan's increased level of international openness, the number of large tourism segments that are still not receiving due attention, that is, those who organize their own trips, will inevitably increase sharply.

In order to increase the attractiveness of Uzbekistan in the eyes of unorganized tourists, the implementation of the following tasks is of paramount importance:

There is a need to implement and improve existing facilities and national systems that provide broad access to reservation systems and the purchase of essential services. Such as hotel services, restaurants, purchasing and booking air and rail tickets, entrance tickets to attractions online.

Since self-organized tourists, as a rule, use innovative guide services along with traditional ones and prefer to receive these services through audio guides, museum information kiosks, mobile applications, it is necessary to widely introduce them into practice;

Unlike organized tourists, self-organized tourists eat on occasion, impromptu, therefore, it is recommended to introduce the same type of fast food outlets, given that they prefer to use the services of nearby cafes and bars in places of tourist interest;

Given the increasing number of trips carried out by private, rented vehicles, it is necessary to introduce high-capacity parking and camping in tourist areas;

As a result of the sharp increase in the number of tourists wishing to take advantage of affordable housing services, in the near future there will be a high demand for traditional houses, hostels, apartment rentals, which will require an increase in the number of such services;

Access to travel information is critical in self-guided travel, and the need for widespread use of information kiosks, signage, geolocation systems and tourist police services will increase.

Based on the above findings and expert opinions obtained as a result of studying market trends of proactive tour operators operating in the main markets generating tourists (USA, Germany, Switzerland, France, Italy, UK), a forecast of the types of tourism services for which the need will increase and decrease has been developed by 2030 in Uzbekistan, as shown in Figure 1.

Implementation targeted measures in the above cases will increase the attractiveness of the country for self-organized tourists from 52 countries using a simplified visa regime and 86 countries without visa entry into the country, and also achieve high competitiveness of travel and tourism in Uzbekistan.

Figure 1. Forecast of increase and decrease in the number of types of tourism services in Uzbekistan until 2030 (author's development)

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